

Some Ionophoretic Studies in Presence and Absence of Citrate as a Complexant*

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In earlier communications¹⁻³ the migration of cations, forming anionic complexes, has been studied in presence of added complexants like oxalate, citrate, and tartrate. In the present communication the electromigration of some cations has been investigated in presence of different background electrolytes with citrate added as a complexant. Incidentally, some studies have also been made in absence of citrate.

LKB (type 3276 B) paper electrophoresis equipment was employed, using Pt anode and steel cathode. A power supply unit of the same make (type 3290 B) was used. Carl Schleicher and Schül filter paper No. 2043, 120 g./m.² of size 40 × 410 mm, was used.

Metal solutions were prepared from reagent grade chemicals and standardised by the usual methods. Standard solutions of HCl, KCl, and NaCl as background electrolytes were prepared from B.D.H. AnalaR chemicals.

Procedure.—To 1 ml each of the metal ions (0.1*M*), 1 ml of sodium citrate (1*M*) was added (total volume 5 ml). The movement of the ions was studied, allowing 3 hr. for electrophoresis, using different potentials and background electrolytes. Fig. 1 shows the separations when the voltage applied was 2.44V/cm. The filter paper strip was treated with dithizone in carbon tetrachloride and fumed over ammonia. With increasing voltages, separations were similar, but Bi³⁺ and Cd²⁺ had a tendency to overlap. The results of separations of some ions in absence of citrate are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Final conc. of metal ion = 0.01*M*. Time = 3 hr. Voltage = 6.1V/cm. Reagents: Dithizone in CCl₄ (for 1 and 2), benzidine in acetic acid (for 3, 4, and 5), dimethylglyoxime (for nickel), α -nitroso- β -naphthol (for cobalt). Distances are measured in mm.

Expt No.	Mixtures.	Anionic.		Isoelectric.	Cationic.	
		Hg (II).	Pd (II).	Bi (III).	Cd (II).	Cu (II).
1	Cu(II), Hg(II), Cd(II), & Bi(III)	38-13		±0	10-28	30-45
2	Zn(II), Cd(II) & Hg(II)	Hg(II). 43-20		..	Cd(II). 15-35	Zn(II). 42-64
3	Pt(IV), (Pd(II) & Au(III))	Pt(IV). 68-59	Pd(II). 58-50	Au(III). 31-20	..	..
4	Cu(II) & Au(III)	Au(III). 33-17	..	..	Cu(II). 31-52	..
5	Pd(II) & Au (III)	Pd(II). 62-52	Au (III). 29-20	..	..	..
6	Ni(II) & Co(II)				Ni(II). 40-50	Co(II). 52-61

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The results (Fig. 1) show that anionic citrate complexes of Bi(III), Cd(II), and Cu(II) do not form in an acidic medium, whereas in presence of KCl and NaCl as the background electrolytes, the anionic complexes are formed. This is in conformity with the results of Bobtelsky *et al.*⁴; who noted that a number of citrate complexes investigated by them were stable only above pH 6.0.

Fig. 1. Separation of metal ions in presence of citrate at 2.44 V/cm.
a=0.1N-HCl. b=0.1N-KCl. c=0.1N-NaCl.

Fig. 2. Separation of metal ions in presence of HCl with no added citrate.

The separations carried out in absence of citrate, using 0.1N-HCl as the background electrolyte, show that anionic chloro complexes are formed in cases of Pt(IV), Pd(II), Au(III), and Hg(II), whereas Cu(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), and Cd(II) remain cationic. Some typical separations are shown in Fig. 2. Obviously, the anionic chloro complexes of Pt(IV), Pd(II), Au(III) and Hg(II) are formed in the same way as in the case of Fe(III)⁵.

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